

Origins and relationship of the words “Boat” and “Rest” in various eurasian languages

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Abstract:

In the following article, a series of connections are cited regarding the words rest and boat that may be of interest for future study. The aim is to provide a better understanding of the various cultures and migratory movements that occurred in those times. This work recognizes the difficulties in reconstructing roots so distant in time, and that many reconstructions tend to be hypothetical.

Key words:

Boat, Rest, Indoeuropean, Semitic

The idea is discussed that Afroasiatic languages contributed loans to Indo-European (IE), as several authors have shown (Björn R. 2021). It is well known that there is a hypothesis that has long generated debate, called the Nostratic hypothesis, in which linguist Sergei Starostin proposed that several language families came from a larger family that was possibly spoken somewhere in Eurasia at the end of the Paleolithic, and may have diversified thanks to agriculture. Alternatively, this hypothesis could be better explained as a possibility that contacts occurred among different peoples, which could have produced various linguistic loans.

The word proposed for this study is the Semitic root nVwVḥ- (“to rest”) and the Indo-European -naw (“boat”). The following paragraph shows the proposed similarities (Starostin):

- Nostratic: nVḥV (hypothetical) → calm (V. Illich-Svitych & A. Dolgopolsky)
- Proto-Afroasiatic: -naw (hypothetical) → to be tired (Starostin)
- Proto-Semitic: nVwVḥ- → to rest (Starostin), nah(a)r- → river (Alexander Militarev & Leonid Kogan), nVhar- → river (Starostin)
- Proto-Indo-European: nāw- → *boat* (Starostin), néh□-u- → *to flow, to move* (Dagmar S. Wodtko), nāwā → *boat* (Ranko Matasović), nakwan- → *that which floats* (Guus Roonen), (s)neh²- → *to swim, to let flow, to float* (Helmut Rix)
- Egyptian: nw → *weak* (Starostin)
- Hebrew: nwh → *rest* (Starostin)

- Germanic: *nōwa-z* → *boat, vessel* (Starostin)

Possible explanation for these phenomena include:

The word may have traveled across distant regions, functioning as a wanderwort of Afroasiatic origin. In Prehistory, human movements were common, and various symbols traveled long distances, explaining the presence of similar themes in myths (e.g., snake, flood, swastika, etc.) in diverse parts of the world. The word *tea* would be an example of this.

Possibly, Middle Eastern migrants brought words to Ukraine, or the ancestors of the Yamnaya encountered other ethnic groups with different languages during migration. Recent studies show that inhabitants of the Ukrainian steppes received a significant genetic contribution from the Caucasus. As several authors in various journals have mentioned, there is evidence that both Indo-European and Uralic groups had contact while migrating from Siberia to Scandinavia, as well as ancestors of Indo-Europeans and Afroasiatic groups in the northern Zagros area, the Caucasus, and the Taurus Mountains. In fact, a recent publication showed that some Yamnaya groups originated from the Caucasus, contributing CLV genetic components to various steppe populations.

There is also the possibility that these words originate from the same linguistic stock and diversified over time.

Thus, this root could have evolved into other words, creating false cognates, as shown in the following terms of Indo-European or Latin origin:

- Actual (English; what happens now) and actual (Spanish; that which is present) → actualis (Latin)
- To embarrass (English; to feel ashamed, uncomfortable) and embarazar (Spanish; to impregnate a woman) → embarrasser (French; to obstruct) → barra (Latin)
- Rope (English; cord) and ropa (Spanish; clothing) → reup- / reupə- (Indo-European; to wind, roll)

Additionally, several words could be mentioned as:

- h₂stér (IE) and attar (PS): star
- Tawros (IE) and tawr (PS): bull
- wóyh₂-no (IE) and wayn- (PS): wine

In this case, it is suggested that this is a linguistic loan, where the word passed into Indo-European or vice versa possibly due to semantic similarity. The semantic association between calm waters and rest may have influenced lexical development in these languages. Several studies demonstrate this effect, as the sea acts as a relaxant, similar to being in the mountains, because the brain

reacts similarly when exposed to nature including that the word could have developed from other unknown roots.

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